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Sociological Investigation of the Tendency to Have a Premarital Relationship with the Opposite Sex and the Factors Affecting It (A case study of male and female students of the second secondary level in Khalkhal high schools)

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Abstract

The purpose of this article is to study the tendency towards premarital relationships among boys and girls. This issue was investigated and researched as a case study in Khalkhal high schools. Our study method was a survey. Our statistical population of all girls' and boys' high schools in the second stage of high school included 2532 people who were selected using systematic sampling and using Cochran's formula, 346 people from each school in one or two classes. Our measuring tool was a researcher-made questionnaire, and its validity was formalized by sociological experts. The reliability of our questionnaire and variables was 0.66 to 0.85, which shows the reliability, capability and reliability of the tool. The value of the correlation coefficient of the regression model was equal to 0.807. The coefficient of determination is equal to 0.651; That is, 0.651 of dependent variable changes are explained by independent variables. And 0.349% depends on other factors, considering that the dependent variable is more influential than the family encouragement variable, it can be said that family encouragement has the greatest impact on the amount of premarital relationship with the opposite sex compared to other variables. According to the significance level of three independent variables of friends' agreement (0.000), family encouragement (0.000) and religious adherence (0.000) is less than 0.05, all independent variables have an effect on the dependent variable of premarital relationships.

Key words: relationship, relationship before marriage, anklet.

Introduction

In all societies, the way of relationship with the opposite sex has been of special importance and has taken a special form in every historical period. Many western industrialized countries do not consider it appropriate to use instinct control, but it seems that this situation has also brought new problems for them. But we have to see how this situation is in our country and city? Does the traditional and religious culture of Iran, the material level of culture or technology and the speed of their arrival have any effect on such relations? In this article, the problem is, what is the type of behavioral tendency of girls and boys and what causes can it have, and how do they act in finding these behaviors?

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Psychologists and sociologists have proposed reasons and benefits such as companionship, relationship, increasing social status and choosing a spouse in such relationships. But in many cases, these benefits become harmful and this problem is formed due to ignorance and ignorance of how to deal with the opposite sex and the negative consequences of it. Sometimes such friendships are formed only for the purpose of entertainment, and girls' self-confidence and gullibility are used badly.

Other consequences of such relationships are academic failure, suspicion towards the future spouse, feelings of betrayal towards the spouse after marriage, suicide, anxiety, depression, low self-esteem and reduced relationship with the family. These same issues determine the necessity of teaching how to communicate with the opposite sex. The study of Ramana Krishna, Karput and Murphy (2006) also insists, having relationships with the opposite sex causes distance from the family. Nelson and Wampler also found that people who had sexual intercourse with the opposite sex before marriage. He did not perform well towards his wife and their disordered situation had a negative effect on the behavior of their wives.

In recent decades, the relationship between boys and girls has been a social problem. Home and school supervisors have been constantly faced with the problem of how to keep boys and girls away from each other until marriage. For them and especially the parents of girls, this question has always been a plan of what to do so that teenagers and young people do not establish relationships with people in an illegitimate and unconventional way. In a few cases, we have witnessed the suicide of girls and boys for this reason. (Ahmadi, 2003: 31)

In societies where there is a lot of complexity and variety of behavior, there are various patterns in front of teenagers, and they face a problem in choosing one or more patterns for identification. In simple societies such as rural and nomadic societies, identification of teenagers faces fewer problems, because the patterns in such societies do not have many varieties. In such societies, there are several types of jobs and few personalities, such as stereotypes for teenagers, that teenagers can identify with when dealing with problems. Therefore, in the simple societies of Iran, we often come across 14 or 15-year-old youths who behave like the men and women of that society and behave or express their opinions in their company. In other words, we should say that in simple societies, the period of adolescence is shorter in terms of identification, and in complex societies this period is longer. The weakening of the family foundation in the West, the prevalence of cohabitation; It means families where a man and a woman live with each other for a period of time without a formal or customary marriage and do not have any commitments or restrictions for their solid and long-term life, the prevalence of homosexuality and its legalization, and the practice of living alone. The whole thing is a warning for us and the future ahead of us. Today, some western governments and politicians are trying to save the nuclear family.

According to some educational and social science thinkers, the formation of close and romantic relationships is an important task and social development for teenagers. As children enter adolescence, the time spent with peers of the opposite sex (heterosexual) increases. From the middle to the end of adolescence, this heterosexual interaction turns into romantic interests and romantic relationships are formed. It is not surprising that the proportion of teenagers who have a boyfriend or girlfriend also increases at this time. Today, young people have rejected most of the values of adults and have found other values and issues that shape the subject of their work and means of communication. The normal tasks of daily life that involve us in face-to-face and more or less continuous interaction with others. Therefore, our daily activities and the interactions that we engage in with the opposite sex build and shape what we do. We can learn something about ourselves as social beings and social life itself from examining them. Let's learn a lot. Establishing a healthy relationship with others is one of the personal and moral achievements of every person. (Ritzer, 2003: 237)

Research literature

Background research

Various researches carried out in Iran inform about extensive but hidden changes under the skin of the city and among the urban youth.

1- Farideh Khalajabadi Farahani conducts a research in 2013 titled the effect of relationship with the opposite sex before marriage on the probability of divorce among university educated people. The results of his research show that the experience of premarital relationship among educated people who are about to divorce is significantly more than among educated people who have a wife and this percentage is 3.8 among those who are about to divorce. It is more than people who do not have the mentioned experience. (Khalaj Farahani, 2012: 49)

2- Siderkunuddin Rashidi Al Hashem has conducted a research titled social disorder and its effect on sexual perversions in Qom in 2013. The results of his research show that immigration, population growth and spatial changes within the city have led to sexual perversions in this city.(Rashidi, 2012)

3- Taghi Azad Aramaki, Mohammad Hossein Sharifi Sa'i, Maryam Ithari and Sahar Talebi (2013) have conducted a research titled "Genology of Premarital Sexual Relations Patterns in Iran". The results of their research show that premarital sexual relations in Among young people, it has increased in recent years, the increase of these behaviors has increased the complexity of these behaviors, new types of relationships can be seen that have different origins. Prostitution patterns, concubine relationships, girlfriend-boyfriend relationships, housemate relationships, anti-romantic relationships (patterns of deception) and relationships based on fluid love are among them.(Azad Armaki and society, 2011:1)

4- Omid Qaderzadeh, Fardin Mohammadi and Hossein Mohammadi conducted a research in 2016 with the title of qualitative study of the contexts, interactions and consequences of premarital relationships of young people, the results of their research show that premarital young people Due to emotional problems, intensification of sexual desires and membership and facilitating acceptance in the group of friends, they have turned to sex with the opposite sex. (Ghaderzade, Mohammddi, Mohammadi, 2017:7)

5- Behrooz Behroozian and Ehsan Hasanvand have conducted a research titled "Semantic Reconstruction of Premarital Relationships: Presenting a Grounded Theory" in 2014. The results of the research show that new communication tools, peer group pressure, leisure behavior, sexual identification, emotional needs, romantic relationships, opportunity and possibility of communication, transfer of value goals with gender liberation values to pre-marriage relationships help. they do.(: 17 Behroozian, Hasanvand, 2016)

Researches outside the academic centers of the country have also obtained similar results:

1- Harding and Jenks (2003) have conducted a research entitled Attitudinal change towards premarital sexual relations. The results of his research show that in 1969, more than 75 percent of Americans considered premarital sex to be an ugly and disgusting thing, but only after a few years, the dominant view of the Americans has clearly changed in this way. that in the 1980s, only 33% of Americans considered premarital sex to be inappropriate, and in today's society, almost all teenagers have experienced premarital sex.(Harding, Genks, 2003, 211-226)

2- Goman, Levy, Hoi and Knadel (2006) have conducted a research entitled the continuation and transformation of premarital sexual relations in Vietnam. The results of the research show that in the current few decades, premarital sexual relations in developing countries Progress like Vietnam has not only increased, but their pattern has changed. In the past, such relationships were mostly limited to sex workers, but today's young people in Vietnam are more interested in having sex with someone they want to marry. 42 25% of North Vietnamese men and 25% of South Vietnamese men had sex with their current spouse before marriage.(Ghuman, Loi, Huy, Knodel, 2006: 166-174)

3- Farzichi (2000) has done a research titled changing sexual relations between boys and girls. The results of his research show that the proportion of young Americans who are involved in romantic relationships before marriage has increased from 4% in adolescence to 40%. 50% reaches the age of 16. (Fritsche. Y. 2000: 181-220))

4- Belsk and Bass (2001) have conducted a research titled friendship with the opposite sex and concluded in their research that men's motivation to get to know and start a relationship with the opposite sex is sexual interest, but women are more motivated by They seek such relationships to obtain support and physical care for themselves. (Bleske, Buss, 2000:1310-1323)

5-Alexander (2007) has done a research called the correlation coefficient of sexual relations among unmarried young people. In his research, he has shown that similar processes of value transformations have been

experienced in India after the economic transformations in the past few decades. In the past, the revelation of premarital sex led to a moral scandal, but in the current decades, such a negative view of men has gradually disappeared, while virgin girls retain such a taboo (Alesaner, & society, 2007: 150-159)

Theoretical Framework

The theories that supported our hypotheses in the form of a theoretical framework were: The theory of cultural and value transformation and transformation proposed and developed by Ronald Inglehart, this theory seeks to understand the how and why of cultural change and transformations and the values and attitudes of societies. Regarding the change of cultures, he believes that every culture shows people's attitude in harmony with their environment and this attitude responds to political, economic and technological changes in the long term. People's worldview does not depend only on what their elders teach them, but their worldview is formed by the general experiences of their lives, and sometimes the constructive experiences of a young generation are deeply different from the experiences of previous generations. (Inglehart, 2004). Although Inglehart insists more on the effect of technological and economic changes in the attitudinal and value changes of societies (especially western ones), he also mentions the role of another factor, which he calls the cultural and social heritage of societies. called (Inglehart, Beiker, 2001: 19 20)

His theorizing approach considers two systematic levels (society structure) and micro level (individuals). In this way, environmental and macro changes in the society system have led to changes at the individual level, and these changes have consequences for the system at the micro level. In the totality of the theory of attitudinal and value transformation, Inglehart has two predictive hypotheses that explain the transformation of values: 1) Scarcity hypothesis: based on which a person's priorities are a reflection of his social and economic environment, and the person has the highest value. It is considered for things that are in short supply. 2) Sociability hypothesis: This principle is based on the premise that the major values of the individual, in a broad form, reflecting the situations and processes in the years before puberty, have experienced (Inglehart, 2000: 2210) Therefore, the hypothesis of social acceptance is that scarcity refers to short-term transformations with periodic effects, periods of economic prosperity lead to increased materialism and periods of scarcity (economic recession) lead to materialism, and the hypothesis Socialization implies the existence of long-term generational effects (Engelhart, 2004: 65; Azad & Ghaffari, 2004: 32).

He mentions that metamaterialistic values reflect a person's sense of mental security and not only the level of economic progress (socio-economic base), the person's sense of security is caused by the cultural background and social welfare of the institutions in which he lives. It has grown and grown. Thus, the scarcity hypothesis should be supported by the sociability hypothesis. The main structure of a person's personality is formed before puberty, and after that relatively few changes take place (Inglehart, 2000:221). They have constructive security, that is, those who are responsible for the economic and life security of people, whose value priorities are meta-materialistic, because they have assumed material and life security for granted. Therefore, a set of other needs are planned for them. Needs such as self-improvement, love and attachment, which are high-level needs. They are people which give great importance to human choice. But materialists are people who have materialistic priorities due to not having a sense of constructive security - arising from the time of their personality formation and the current economic situation. They insist more on economic and life security (11 Inglehart, 2004:) This leads to very different orientations of materialists and metamaterialists towards many social, political and economic issues and their attitudes towards Many of the traditional gender norms such as illicit sexual relations, prostitution, abortion, divorce, etc. As a broad generalization, it can be stated that Madians support traditional norms much more than Trans-Madians (Inglehart, 2004: 222).

In his new works, he talks about two basic and major dimensions of intercultural values, which are related to the processes of modernism and trans-culturalism. Based on this, the value orientations of people can be compared with each other based on these two dimensions. These two dimensions are:

1. Traditional values against the values of this rational world

2. Enduring values against self-improvement values (Ingelhart, 2004:11)

Kejroi is considered as a threat to the stability of the social system and in the direction of disrupting the existing social order. The basic concept in this type of explanation is that the general structure of society causes special groups of people to find themselves with basic inequalities in special types of opportunities to achieve accepted goals. This is also while the society itself valued those goals and was and is their promoter (Zakarriaei, 20005: 35) including structural-functional explanations based on it in areas with high levels of delinquency. This phenomenon is more or less in the form of traditional and social aspects. Traditions that are transmitted to people through individual and group interactions and the most important aspects of achieving this process also occur in small groups and delinquent youth groups (Seddig, 1995: 021). And this theory justifies deviance as a behavior that is learned like conformity, that is, it is learned by interacting with other people. As a result, the antithesis theory comes close to the insights of the proponents of symbolic interaction and uses them for the process of deviant socialization

Abnormalities appear in situations where there are no clear criteria to guide behavior in certain areas of social life. In Durkheim's opinion, the consequences of anomie can be revealed in the form of mental and personal disorder and in the form of the conflict between the individual and selfish personality of a human being and his social and other-loving personality. The result of this conflict is that the demands of the collective conscience (which, in addition to the influence of the individual's social and selfish personality, controls the motivating forces of his individual and selfish personality) loses its effectiveness. The reduction of these obligations and pressures also causes people to be left alone, and this is where unlimited desires break the reins, and put pressure on a person to engage in behaviors such as laziness or suicide, phenomena that Durkheim calls the same. Ignoring the requirements of the collective conscience. In this way, one of the implied meanings of Durkheim's theory of "abnormality" is that unlimited desires put pressure on people to deviate from social norms (Zakarriaei, 20005: 31).

According to Durkheim, the obvious reason for the formation of anomie is accelerated economic transformations, and this is because these transformations lead to a kind of crisis in the value and normative system of society, and not because "production creates poverty". In his opinion, the phenomenon of poverty, without the intervention of other variables, plays the role of a "stabilizing factor" in the society. But in this situation, the consequences of the formation of these accelerated transformations, elements such as "sudden riches" are against it, elements that make the existence of poverty "unbearable". So, when elements such as "ambitious dreams" become "images" or "promises" in addition to this unbearable poverty, the phenomenon structure of people's needs collapses and the formation of "immeasurable desires" is the product of this situation and the beginning of anomie. It takes the power to control this structure from the "traditional normative system", in this situation, the needs are not satisfied, that is where legitimate and illegitimate means are used to get rid of that "intolerable situation" (ibid). The situation that the diagram below has briefly explained.

The hypotheses derived from the theoretical framework of the research that were in sync with the research objectives are:

- 1- The age of students has an effect on their premarital relationships with the opposite sex.
- 2- The gender of students has an effect on their premarital relationships with the opposite sex
- 3- The educational level of students has an effect on their premarital relationships with the opposite sex.
- 4- Where students live has an effect on their premarital relationships with the opposite sex
- 5- The socio-economic base of students has an effect on their premarital relationships with the opposite sex.
- 6- Students' religious adherence has an effect on their premarital relationships with the opposite sex.
- 7- The compatibility of students with friends has an effect on their premarital relationships with the opposite sex.

8- Encouraging students' families has an effect on their premarital relationships with the opposite sex

Research methods

The current research was conducted as a correlational survey. The operational definitions of the variables used in this research are: premarital relationships with the opposite sex: regarding premarital relationships with the opposite sex, variables such as the need to be loved, the need to have friendly relations, pleasure seeking , getting to know the opposite sex, loneliness, gaining experience, and filling free time are in the top ranks, and establishing marriage, which seemed to be the main factor in establishing a relationship.

Religious adherence: Religious adherence means believing in religious programs and behaving within the framework of this program. Religious adherence or religiosity can be measured on two levels of belief and behavior. In the current research, people's religiosity has been measured at the level of behavior and belief. Among the operational indicators of this variable are praying, fasting, believing in resurrection, participating in congregational prayers, fasting, reading births, being a member of religious bodies, believing in the principle of the Day of Resurrection, believing in forbidden and permissible, believing in the forgiveness of sins. And also the measurement level in this variable is at the rank level.

Socio-economic base: the current status of a person is in the social hierarchy (Zokaei & Mirzaei, 2005: 81). To measure this concept, the level of education, monthly income and occupational status of parents are used, which is the level of measuring the socio-economic base of parents. Students are ranked. Group of peers and friends: Accepted models of a person in the way of speech, actions, behavior and manners. In order to be accepted by the group of friends and peers and have a relationship with them, a person must accept their norms and values. Otherwise, it will be removed from that collection. Therefore, it is strongly affected by that group, to the extent that if there is a change in the individual's behavior, or the norms and values of that group must be changed, or the individual's relationship with that group must be cut off.

The statistical population of the research is all the students of the second secondary schools of Khalkhal, whose number is equal to 2532 (Information of Khodaverdifar of Khalkhal Amozesh va Parvareh, 2014) and Cochran's formula was used to estimate the sample size, which is described below. In the present study, proportional systematic sampling was used. In the first stage, the number of students of each school was divided by the total statistical population and then by multiplying by the total sample size, each school's share of the sample size was estimated. In the second stage, the classes of each school were numbered and according to the required sample size of that school, 1 or 2 classes were randomly selected from each school.

Table No. 1 estimation of sample size

Name of school, type of school, number of students, number of samples
229 32 girls' seminary
Boy's knowledge 222 30
141 20
122 17 Kardanesh Union College
Girls' dresses 63 9
Kemal Pesarane 95 13
Farzangan al-Zahra for girls 126 17
Shahid bahner boys 195 27
Ali Ibn Abitaleb boy's government sample 183 25
Shahid Beheshti Boys 158 21
Muhaddith for girls 121 16

The brilliant talents of Shahid Beheshti, boys, 158 21

Fadek/Fadak for girls 270 37

161 22. Government sample of Atrat for girls

Bagheral Uloom for girls 288 39

Total by gender and the total number of girls 1258 172

Total son 1274 174

Total sum 2532 346

Questionnaire tools have been used to measure relationships and influence of variables. The tool chosen in this research to collect information is a face-to-face questionnaire, for this purpose, after preparing the preliminary questionnaire, its preliminary test and the final questionnaire, data was collected. The questionnaire was in the form of a Likert scale.

Using the face validity of the prepared questionnaire, it was given to a number of expert and selected professors of sociology, and their agreement on the indicators is a clear proof of the validity of the designed questionnaire. Reliability of the research with Cronbach's alpha. First, a sample of 30 questionnaires was selected among the students completely randomly and distributed (pre-test), then it was analyzed with Cronbach's alpha using spss software. which is as follows:

Table No. 2 - Cronbach's alpha coefficient of independent and dependent research variables

Variable	index alpha
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The agreement of students with friends is 0.73%

Encouragement of the family on the relationship with the opposite sex 0.71%

Religious adherence of students 0.66%

Tendency to premarital relationship with the opposite sex 0.73%

Considering that the alpha coefficient of dependent variable indices was 0.73% and independent variables was 0.85%; Therefore, the designed objects have the necessary reliability. findings

Descriptive findings

Separating the sample with the variable of social and economic base According to the data in Table No. 3, it shows the variable distribution of the social and economic base of the respondents, most of them, 186 students, have an average social and economic base, which includes 53.8% of the sample size, and the lowest of them is 62 The number of students has a high social and economic base, which includes 17.9 percent of the sample size. Table No. 3- Distribution of respondents according to social and economic base

The social and economic basis of frequency of percentage

Low social and economic base 3/28 98

Average social and economic base 186 53/8

High social and economic base 62 9/17

Total 346 0.100

Separating the sample with the relationship variable of students before marriage with the opposite sex According to the data of table number 4, in the separation of the sample with the variable of premarital relationship of the students with the opposite sex of the respondents, it shows that out of the total number of respondents, 116 of the students chose the option I agree, which is 33.5% of the sample size. The least of them, i.e. 14 people, chose the completely opposite option, which is 4% of the sample size.

Table No. 4- Distribution of respondents according to premarital relationship with the opposite sex premarital relationship with the opposite sex, percentage frequency

I completely disagree 0.14 4

I disagree 52 0.15

About 108 31/2

I agree 116 33/5

I completely agree. 56 2/16

Total 346 0.100

Separation of the sample with attitude towards the variable of premarital relationship with the opposite sex According to the data in Table No. 5- in the sample separation according to the attitude of the respondents on premarital relationship with the opposite sex, it shows that 172 students have a favorable attitude on premarital relationship with the opposite sex, which is 49.7% of the sample size. and 108 people have an average attitude regarding premarital relationship with the opposite sex, which is 31.2% of the sample size, and 66 people have an opposite attitude regarding premarital relationship with the opposite sex, which is 18.2% of the sample size.

Table No. 5- The distribution of respondents according to the attitude of students' compatibility with their friends and relatives

Attitude towards premarital relationship with the opposite sex, percentage frequency
I disagree 66 1/19

About 108 31/2

I agree 172 49/7

Total 346 100

Separating the sample according to the variable of compatibility of students with their friends and relatives in premarital relationship with the opposite sex

According to the data of table number 6- in separating the sample with the variable of compatibility of students with their friends and relatives in pre-marital relationships with the opposite sex, it shows that the most of the total respondents, i.e. 119 of the students, chose the option I agree, which is 4/ They have allocated 34% of the sample volume, and the least of them, that is, 17 people, have chosen the completely opposite option, which is 4.9% of the sample volume.

Table No. 8- Distribution of the respondents according to the family's encouragement to communicate with the opposite sex Consistency of students with their friends and relatives, frequency of percentage

I completely disagree 12 3/5

I disagree 47 13/6

About 0.26 90

I agree 124 35/8

I completely agree. 73 21/1

Total 346 100.0

Separation of the sample with attitude towards the variable of family encouragement in premarital **relationship with the opposite sex**

According to the data of table number 9- in the separation of the sample with the attitude of the students' agreement with the encouragement of the family in the premarital relationship with the opposite sex of the respondents, it shows that 197 of the students have a favorable attitude towards the effect of the encouragement of the family in the premarital relationship. married with the opposite sex, which includes 56.9% of the sample size, and 90 people have an average attitude on the effect of family encouragement in premarital relationship with the opposite sex, which includes 33.5% of the sample size, and 59 people have an opposite attitude In the effect of family encouragement in premarital relationship with the opposite sex, it is 17.1% of the sample size.

Table No. 9- Distribution of the respondents according to their attitude towards the encouragement of the family on the relationship with the opposite sex

Encouragement of the family on the relationship with the opposite sex, the frequency of the percentage

I disagree 59 1/17

About 0.26 90

I agree 197 56/9

Total 346 0.100

Separating the sample with the variable of students' religious adherence According to the data of table no. 10, in separating the sample with the variable of students' religious adherence, it shows the respondents that out of all the respondents, 131 of the students chose the option to some extent, which is 37.9% of the sample volume. and the least of them, i.e. 19 people, chose the completely opposite option, which is 5.5% of the sample size.

Table No. 10- Distribution of respondents according to students' religious affiliations

Religious adherences of students, percentage frequency

I completely disagree. 19 5/5

I disagree 77 22/3

Some 131 37/9

I agree. 5/27/95

I completely agree. 24/6/9

Total 346 0.100

Separating the sample with the attitude of students' religious affiliations According to the data of table number 10, in the separation of the sample with the attitude towards the religious adherence of the students, it shows that 119 of the students have a favorable attitude towards religious adherence, which is 34.4% of the sample size, and 131 students have an attitude of They have an average religious adherence, which includes 37.9% of the sample size, and 96 people have an opposite attitude in religious adherence, which is 27.7% of the sample size.

Table No. 10- Distribution of respondents according to the attitude towards students' religious adherence Attitudes towards religious adherence of students, frequency of percentage
I disagree 7/27/96

Some 131 37/9

I agree 119 34/4

Total 346 0.100

Inferential findings

The first hypothesis

The age of students has an effect on their premarital relationship with the opposite sex. According to the data of table number 11, which in the Pearson correlation test, the age of the students and their premarital relationship with the opposite sex $r=0.127$ and at the significant level obtained from the test ($\alpha=0.018$) which from the level The desired significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) is smaller, indicating that the age of the students has a weak effect on their premarital relationship. Such an effect is increasing, but its effect is small.

Table No. 11- Pearson's correlation test of the effect of age on the premarital relationship with the opposite sex Their association with the opposite sex before marriage is the independent variable $r= 0.127(*)$ Age

sig=0.018

N=346

The second hypothesis

Gender has an effect on students' premarital relationship with the opposite sex. According to the data in table number 12, it can be seen that in the T-test the effect of pre-marital relationship with the opposite sex is $T=0.056$ and at the significance level obtained from the test ($\alpha=0.955$) which is less than the desired significance level ($0.5 \alpha = 0$) is larger, indicating that gender has no effect on the degree of relationship between students before marriage with the opposite sex.

Table No. 11- T-test of the effect of gender on the premarital relationship of students with the opposite sex Type, number, mean, standard deviation, mean difference, degrees of freedom, T value, significance level

Boy 20/47 174 0624/0624 8/234 056/0 955/0

Girl 172 47/15 8/267 /0630

The third hypothesis

The level of education has an effect on the degree of relationship students have with the opposite sex before marriage.

According to the data in Table No. 12, it can be seen that in the variance analysis test, the criterion error of the second level of education is more than the rest of the levels of education, so the dispersion of relationships with the opposite sex before marriage is more in the second level. And according to the significance level of the test ($\alpha = 0.000$) which is smaller than the desired significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$), it shows that there is a significant difference between the four levels of education in relation to the opposite sex before marriage.

There is.

Table No. 12-variance analysis test, there is a difference between the level of education and the amount of socializing of students with the opposite sex before marriage.

Grade
Sample
Average

The standard deviation

The standard error of average premarital intercourse in

Main community with 95% confidence

The lowest limit is the highest limit

First grade 60 47/48 7/259/0937 45/61 49/36

Second level of education 79 24/44 8/385/0943 42/36 12/46

Third grade 97 46/71 9/074/0921 44/88 48/54

Fourth grade 110 49/51 7/171/0684 48/15 50/86

Social trust, sum of constraints, degree of freedom, means constraints, F value, significance level among the group

Within the group 117/1306 822/22102 737/6 372/43564/628 6/737 0.000

The fourth hypothesis

The place where students live has an effect on their premarital relationship with the opposite sex. According to the data in table number 13, it can be seen that in the T-test, the place of residence on the relationship of students before marriage with the opposite sex is $T=0.214$ and at the significant level obtained from the test ($\alpha=0.831$), which is from the significant level of the case The opinion ($\alpha = 0.05$) is bigger, indicating that the place of residence and the amount of socializing of students before marriage with the opposite sex has no effect.

Table No. 13- T-test of the place of residence and the degree of relationship of the students before marriage with the opposite sex

Place of residence, mean number, standard deviation, mean difference, degree of freedom, T value, significance level

City 24/47/232 040/040/0528 344 0/214/0 831/0

Village 114 47/04 8/659 /0811

The fifth hypothesis

The socio-economic base of students has an effect on the level of their premarital relationship with sex. According to Table 14, the significance level obtained from the test ($\alpha=0.936$) which is greater than the desired significance level ($\alpha=0.05$) shows that among the three socio-economic bases of students in the amount of socializing Before they marry the opposite sex, there is no difference.

Table No. 14- Variance analysis test between socio-economic base and the amount of socializing with the opposite sex before marriage

Socio-economic base

Sample
Average

The standard deviation

The standard error of average premarital intercourse in Main community with 95% confidence

The lowest limit is the highest limit

Lower floor 47/98 7/985/0807 45/40 48/60

middle class 16/47/186 275/8/0607 96/45 35/48

upper floor 62 47/48 8/634 1/097 45/29 68/49

Table No. 14 of Anva

Social trust, the total of constraints in 9 degrees of freedom, the mean of constraints, F value, significance level among the group Within the group of 977/8

962/23399 2

343 488/4

68.221, 0.066, 0.936

The sixth hypothesis

The level of religious adherence of students and the level of their relationship with the opposite sex before marriage has an effect. According to the data of Table No. 15, which in the Pearson correlation test, the relationship between students' religious adherence and their relationship with the opposite sex before marriage is $r=0.300$ and at the significant level obtained from the test ($\alpha=0.000$). It is that there is a relationship between these two variables at the 99% level and the intensity of the relationship is weak. And due to the positive sign of the correlation coefficient, there is a direct relationship between the two variables, that is, with the increase of one, the other also increases and vice versa.

Table No. 15-Pearson's correlation test between students' religious adherence and the amount of socializing with the opposite sex before marriage and the amount of their socializing before marriage with gender as an independent variable

$r= 0.300$ - (**) religious adherence

$sig=0.000$

$N=346$

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

The seventh hypothesis

The level of compatibility of students with their friends and the level of their relationship with the opposite sex before marriage has an effect. According to the data in table number 16, it can be seen that in Pearson's correlation test, the relationship between students' compatibility with students' friends and the level of their relationship with the opposite sex before marriage is $r=0.537$ and at the significant level obtained from the test ($/000 \alpha = 0$) indicates that there is a relationship between these two variables at the 99% level and the intensity of the relationship is moderate. And due to the positive sign of the correlation coefficient, there is a direct relationship between the two variables, that is, with the increase of one, the other also increases and vice versa.

Table number 16- Pearson's correlation test between the compatibility of students' friends and their relationship with the opposite sex before marriage and the amount of their socializing before marriage with gender as an independent variable

$r = 0.537$ - (**) Students agree with friends

$sig = 0.000$

$N = 346$

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

The eighth hypothesis

The level of family encouragement has an effect on the relationship with the opposite sex and the level of premarital relationship with the opposite sex. According to the data in Table No. 17, it can be seen that in the Pearson correlation test, the relationship between students' religious adherence and their premarital relationship with the opposite sex is $r = 0.537$ and at the significant level obtained from the test ($\alpha = 0.000$). It indicates that there is a relationship between these two variables at the 99% level and the intensity of the relationship is moderate. And due to the positive sign of the correlation coefficient, there is a direct relationship between the two variables, that is, with the increase of one, the other also increases and vice versa.

Table number 17- Pearson's correlation test between students' religious adherence and their relationship with the opposite sex before marriage and the amount of their socializing before marriage with gender as an independent variable

$r = -0.537$ (**) family encouragement

$sig = 0.000$

$N = 346$

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Investigating the relationship between the dependent variable and the independent variables with the help of regression

According to the data in table number 18, the correlation coefficient of the regression model is equal to 0.807. The value of the coefficient of determination is equal to 0.651, that is, 0.651 of the dependent variable changes are explained by the independent variables, and 0.349 percent depends on other factors.

Table No. 18 - Summary of the model

The coefficient of determination of R Square, the correlation coefficient of R

0.651 0.807

According to the data in Table No. 18, it can be seen that the significance level of the test is 0.000 less than 0.05 and it can be said with 95% confidence that the fitted model is a suitable model and the regression relationship is linear.

Table No. 19, the significance test of each of the variables entered into the model The total degree of freedom model, mean F, significance level

Regression 523/7088 4 908/36 37/027/0000

The remaining 16320/416 341/0468

Total 23408/939 345

According to the data in table no. 20- it can be seen that considering that the degree of influence of the dependent variable is more than the family encouragement variable, it can be said that family encouragement has the greatest effect on the amount of premarital relationship with the opposite sex compared to other variables.

And according to the significance level of the three independent variables of friends' agreement (0.000), family encouragement (0.000) and religious adherence (0.000) is less than 0.05, therefore they enter the regression model and the significance level of the socio-economic base respectively (0.621) is not less than 0.05, so they are not included in the regression model. In order to better compare the variables, we write the model based on standardized beta coefficients:

And because the beta coefficient of family encouragement is higher than the two variables of friends' conformity and religious adherence, we choose this variable as dependent and friend's conformity and religious adherence as independent variables and regress. Considering that religious students with hijab and students with religious families tend to have romantic relationships less than other students, it is suggested to emphasize on religion as a determining factor.

Considering that honesty, integrity, decency, authenticity, and good morals are abstract principles that are emphasized in students' prioritization for establishing a relationship, it is suggested that by operationally defining these concepts and conducting the necessary research, it is possible to measure them by young people. . At the same time, it is necessary to return concepts such as faith, love, science and knowledge to their original position, i.e. the first priorities, through subtle cultural works. Motives such as the need to love, seeking pleasure, and filling free time are among the main motivations of romantic relationships among students. It seems that by strengthening institutions such as the family institution and creating and strengthening the quality of cultural industries, especially the cinema media industry, as well as emphasizing the interactions between families, leisure time can be reduced from these motivations and the strength of the motivation to marry and form a family institution. Added

According to the fact that the students consider the main problems related to the relationship with the opposite sex to be the restrictions in the society, excesses in the relationship, ignorance of how to have a healthy relationship, and the families' misperception of this relationship. People and authorities have mentioned about this issue, sexual abuse only because the purpose of friendship is unclear, there is no definition and boundary of friendship, there is no culture of friendship, sexual intercourse is on whim, it is suggested that the authorities "lack of places where to be able to see each other and families should consider and implement the necessary arrangements in this regard. Considering the fact that the students consider the most important solutions for the relationship with the opposite sex to be freeing young people, principled and reasonable freedom, education to have a healthy relationship and order to recognize the opposite sex, culturalization, the existence of a relationship under the supervision of parents, extremes and Not neglecting the relationship, changing the way of thinking of the ruling system, specifying the purpose of friendship, reducing the prejudices and strictness of families, expanding the healthy environment for establishing a relationship, they did not know, it is suggested to create sensitivity regarding the relationship with the opposite sex. Necessary action should be taken from a child with arrangements regarding operationalizing them or guiding them.

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